

Development and Characterization of a Millet-Based Fermented Beer Using Biryani Spices

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Abstract:

Millets are nutritionally rich and climate-resilient cereals that are gaining attention as sustainable raw materials in industrial biotechnology. This study focuses on the development of a millet-based fermented beverage, using biryani spices, as a simple model for microbial fermentation and value-added product formation. Fermentation was performed using malted millet (Ragi Wheat and Barley-60:20:20) at a ratio of 100 g in 900 mL of water under controlled laboratory conditions. A marked reduction in fermentable sugars was observed, decreasing from 32.3 mg/mL to 14.5 mg/mL after fermentation, indicating effective utilization of the substrate by fermenting microorganisms. Ethanol production reached 2% alcohol by volume (ABV), confirming successful conversion of carbohydrates into alcohol. Fermentation activity was further evidenced by a drop in pH from 6.75 to 5.94 and an increase in titratable acidity to 0.81% expressed as lactic acid. Minor changes in protein content following fermentation suggest biochemical modification of nutrients during microbial metabolism. Overall, the results highlight the potential of millets as an alternative and sustainable fermentation substrate and demonstrate that microbial processing can effectively transform underutilized cereals into value-added fermented products with scope for industrial scalability.

Keywords: Fermentation, Beer, Millet, Ethanol

Introduction

In recent years, the brewing industry has increasingly focused on developing sustainable and nutritionally enriched beverages. Beer is one of the oldest fermented drinks in the world and is produced by the fermentation of cereal-derived sugars using yeast. Traditionally, beer is brewed using barley malt, hops, water, and yeast, which together influence the flavor, aroma, and quality of the final product. However, modern brewing research is exploring the use of alternative grains and adjuncts to improve sustainability and diversify beer characteristics. [1] Cereal grains are essential in brewing because they provide starch that is converted into fermentable sugars during the mashing process. Barley is commonly used due to its high enzymatic activity, particularly α -amylase and β -amylase, which help break down starch into fermentable sugars for yeast metabolism. In addition to barley, grains such as wheat, rice, and maize have been used as

adjuncts to modify flavor, improve extract yield, or reduce production costs. [2] Recently, millets have gained attention as promising alternative brewing grains. Millets such as finger millet (ragi) are drought-resistant, require minimal agricultural inputs, and grow well in semi-arid regions. They are also rich in carbohydrates, minerals, and dietary fiber, making them suitable for developing nutritionally improved fermented beverages. The use of millets in brewing can therefore support sustainable agriculture while enhancing the nutritional value of beer. [3] Studies have shown that millets can be used as adjuncts or partial substitutes for barley in brewing. Since millets generally have lower enzymatic activity than barley, composite grain systems and optimized mashing techniques are often used to ensure efficient starch conversion and fermentation. These approaches allow the production of beers with acceptable alcohol content, unique flavors, and improved sustainability. [4] Overall, the incorporation of millets in brewing represents an important step toward developing innovative, sustainable, and functional beers that meet the evolving preferences of modern consumers. [5]

Methodology

Preparation and Malting of Grains

Barley, finger millet (ragi), and wheat grains were procured from local markets and used as the primary raw materials for brewing. The grains were first washed thoroughly with water to remove dust and impurities. The cleaned grains were soaked in water and then tied in a cloth to allow germination overnight. After germination, the grains were sun-dried and then placed in a hot air oven at 70°C for 6 hours to stop further sprouting. The sprouted rootlets were removed manually, and the dried grains were weighed according to the required composition for brewing. [1]

Roasting and Preparation of Composite Grist

The dried grains were roasted lightly using dry roasting to enhance flavor and improve the malting characteristics. After roasting, the grains were coarsely ground to obtain a composite grist mixture. The composition of the grains was maintained according to the experimental design using barley, finger millet, and wheat in predetermined proportions. [2]

Table1: Composition of ingredients in the beer

Ingredient	Weight
Mash malt(60:20:20)	100 g
Biriyani spices	3.4g
Mineral water	700ml
Jaggery	21g
Yeast	2g

Mashing Process

The roasted grain mixture was placed inside a muslin cloth and kept in a beaker to facilitate the mashing process. In a separate muslin cloth, selected culinary spices including clove, cinnamon, cardamom, star anise, and bay leaves were tied and placed in the same beaker to impart aroma and bitterness. Mineral water was added to the beaker according to the required liquor-to-grist ratio. The mixture was then heated and boiled for approximately 30 minutes at 60–70°C to allow the extraction of soluble compounds and the conversion of starch into fermentable sugars. [3]

Wort Collection and Adjunct Addition

After the initial boiling step, approximately 100 mL of wort sample was collected for preliminary physicochemical analysis. Jaggery was then added as an additional fermentable sugar source, and the mixture was further heated for a short duration to ensure proper dissolution and mixing. The total boiling time of the wort remained approximately 30 minutes at 60–70°C. [4]

Cooling and Fermentation

After boiling, the wort was cooled to a temperature range of 25–30°C. Yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) was then added to initiate fermentation. The fermented mixture (wort) was transferred into clean bottles and sealed appropriately to allow controlled fermentation. The bottles were stored at room temperature and allowed to ferment for approximately 13 days. Fermentation progress was monitored by observing the formation of gas bubbles, which gradually decreased and eventually stopped at the end of fermentation. [5]

Physicochemical Analysis

Samples were analyzed before and after fermentation to evaluate changes in important brewing parameters. The analysis included measurement of fermentable sugars, ethanol content, protein concentration, pH, and total titratable acidity (TTA). These parameters were used to assess the efficiency of fermentation and the overall quality of the millet-based beer produced. [6]

Analytical Parameters and Methods

The wort and fermented beer samples were analyzed before and after fermentation to evaluate changes in physicochemical properties. The pH of the samples was measured using a digital pH meter. Total titratable acidity (TTA) was determined by the acid–base titration method using standard NaOH and phenolphthalein indicator.

The total sugar content was estimated using the DNS (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid) colorimetric method, which measures reducing sugars present in the sample. Protein content was determined using the Kjeldahl method, a standard technique used to estimate total nitrogen and convert it into protein content.

The ethanol concentration in the fermented samples was determined using the distillation method followed by alcohol measurement to evaluate the efficiency of fermentation. All analyses were conducted for both pre-fermented wort samples and post-fermentation beer samples to compare the biochemical changes during the fermentation process.

Results and Discussion

Biochemical analysis of Sample B showed significant changes after fermentation, indicating active yeast metabolism. The fermentable sugar content decreased from 32.3 mg/ml to 14.5 mg/ml, as yeast utilized sugars as a substrate and converted them into ethanol and carbon dioxide during fermentation.

The protein content increased from 2.8 mg/ml to 3.52 mg/ml, which may be due to microbial growth and the release of proteins and enzymes from yeast cells during metabolic activity. Similarly, titratable acidity increased from 0.42% to 0.63%, reflecting the production of organic acids that contribute to flavor and preservation.

A decrease in pH from 6.75 to 5.83 was observed, which corresponds to the accumulation of organic acids during fermentation. In addition, ethanol content increased from 0% to 2% ABV, confirming the successful conversion of sugars into alcohol by yeast.

Overall, the results indicate that fermentation resulted in sugar utilization, alcohol formation, increased acidity, and slight changes in protein content, demonstrating effective fermentation of the cereal-based substrate. fig:

Fig. Comparative graph showing physicochemical parameters of the sample before and after fermentation.

Table 2: Table showing physicochemical parameter results of the sample before and after fermentation

Parameter	Before fermentation	After Fermentation
Fermentable Sugars	32.3 mg/ml	14.5mg/ml
Protiens	2.8mg/ml	3.52mg/ml
Titratable acids	0.42% butyric acid	0.63% lactic acid
pH	6.75	5.83
Ethanol	0%	2% ABV

Conclusion

The analysis of Sample B demonstrates clear biochemical changes during fermentation. The fermentable sugar content decreased from 32.3 mg/ml to 14.5 mg/ml, indicating utilization of sugars by yeast, which resulted in the production of ethanol (2% ABV) and other metabolic by-products. The protein content increased from 2.8 mg/ml to 3.52 mg/ml, likely due to microbial growth and enzyme release during fermentation. Additionally, titratable acidity increased from 0.42% to 0.63%, while pH decreased from 6.75 to 5.83, reflecting the formation of organic acids.

This study successfully demonstrated the preparation and fermentation of a millet-based beverage using barley, finger millet, and wheat as the primary raw materials. The grains were subjected to germination, drying, roasting, and mashing to obtain fermentable wort, which was later fermented using yeast. The addition of selected spices and jaggery contributed to flavor development and provided additional fermentable sugars for the fermentation process.

Physicochemical analysis conducted before and after fermentation showed clear biochemical changes. A reduction in fermentable sugars, increase in ethanol content, rise in titratable acidity, and decrease in pH confirmed the metabolic activity of yeast during fermentation. Slight variations in protein content were also observed, indicating microbial growth and enzymatic activity during the process.

Overall, the results confirm that fermentation effectively transformed the prepared wort into a mildly alcoholic fermented beverage with measurable changes in its biochemical composition. The study highlights the potential of millet and cereal grains as suitable substrates for developing value-added fermented beverages with nutritional and functional benefits.

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